

Sin and Some Contemporary Western Philosophers

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Introduction

“Hence believers can have more than a little to do with the birth of atheism. To the extent that they neglect their own training in the faith, or teach erroneous doctrine, or are deficient in their religious, moral, or social life, they must be said to conceal rather than reveal the authentic face of God and religion”¹. These sobering words of Vatican II afford us plenty of food for thought.

In traditional circles, ‘atheist’ was taken to be synonymous with an evil person. Recall the words of that character in Dostoevsky’s epic *The Brothers Karamazov*, who affirms, “If God did not exist, anything would be permitted.” The drama of atheistic humanism² assures us that atheists can be very moral people, indeed. As a matter of fact, atheists like Camus (whose views we will be going into a moment) might even say that religious belief is, if anything, ‘an easy way out’, in the face of the contemporary disturbing scenario. In other words, some people are atheists because they want to follow higher and nobler values. This, at least, is how they would see it.

In this brief paper, I want to examine how some well-known contemporary atheists have a place for moral life and nobler values and how they even entertain some kind of concept of sin, even though they would never employ the term. I’ll take some representatives of the atheistic trend in Existentialism and Postmodernism that are not yet spent forces by a long chalk!

A. Some Existentialists

Existentialism is not necessarily atheist. Even Sartre recognized Marcel and Jaspers as religious believers³, but when he went on to claim Heidegger as a fellow-atheist⁴, the latter was swift and peremptory in his rejection of that name⁵. We'll come back to Sartre in a moment.

Albert Camus (1913-1960)

Algerian born, Camus fought his way to the top of the literary world from very humble, impoverished beginnings, winning the Nobel Prize for Literature in 1957. If the whole western world mourned his death in a road accident barely three years later, it was not merely because he was so young and gifted. Rather, people had come to see, in his writings, a certain nobility of spirit and a courageous resolve against totalitarianism, injustice and those perplexities that seemed to be clouding up people's horizons everywhere. Some would even go as far as to brand him 'an atheist saint'.

Now, from one point of view, this is all rather odd. After all, the works of the atheistic Camus represent a rather dark and hopeless kind of pessimism, a pessimism that stems from the fact that the world is basically meaningless and ruthless, for there is no God, no guiding spirit that is able to bring a sense of overall purposiveness into the sorry scheme of things. Everything is ruled by a 'cruel mathematics' whereby the forces of injustice and hatred are numerically stronger and more powerful than those of justice and love; hence, in the last analysis, all that is good and true and beautiful will be swallowed up in a vast all destroying barbarism and chaos will exult in a mocking *danse macabre* on the graves of all utopian dreams and plans.

But now comes the greatness of Camus' vision. Precisely because there is no God to fight on our side, precisely because there is no retributive afterlife to restore some semblance of balance in things, precisely for these reasons, it is humans who must boldly and defiantly strike a blow for harmony and peace...even if we know this would ultimately be a forlorn and futile gesture. Humans must not cow before the 'Absurd'. Since there is no God to take care of the 'little ones', the poor, the widow, the dispossessed and the orphan, *I* must: there is no one else; this recalls those disturbing words of Levinas, which would

come much later: 'we are all responsible (for each other), but I most of all.' Derrida was to avow that these words made him tremble in fear.

The Stranger (1942) and *The Fall* (1957) with their long monologues could hardly be cited as evidence in favour of such a vision, though some critics have tried hard to do so. It was rather novels, like *The Plague* (1947), and reflective pieces like *The Rebel* (1951) and *The Myth of Sisyphus* (1942), which advocated it so powerfully and compellingly. One could see in Dr. Rieux, who alone struggles to assist the plague-stricken people, not having much to offer and knowing that he is fighting a losing battle (even if he is able to somehow save them from the clutches of the fatal illness, isn't he but postponing the inevitable – death?), as a symbol of, or a spokesperson for, Camus? When asked why he does all this self-sacrificing noble service, since he doesn't believe in God or eternal reward, his answer – in a nutshell – is that is precisely the reason he does this. This is all the life we have and there is no God to come to our aid, so it's up to us to do the best we can to make the *lacryma rerum* a little more bearable, a little less agonising⁶. And it is in his provocative and challenging reflection on *The Rebel* that Camus points out that the most radical of all is the 'metaphysical rebel'⁷ – the one who revolts against the whole metaphysical order of the Absurd. For Camus, the human person must not capitulate before the Absurd, humans must not be abandoned to their pitiful metaphysical condition. Even if it's an 'unbeatable foe' that we know we are fighting, we still must fight. In the last analysis, it is Sisyphus⁸ who emerges as our model, the symbol of the indomitable human spirit that labours on to realise a goal that he knows he will never be able to achieve, yet he sees that surrender would be the greatest defeat of all. As long as we battle on, the Absurd cannot claim to have won.

Sin, then, in Camus vocabulary (though he spells it out in so many terms) would be to turn one's back on the struggle against injustice, hypocrisy and tyranny. Sin is to throw in the sponge and surrender before the forces of evil and destruction arrayed against us. Virtue would be to fight on the last, to go down fighting before an invincible foe, to deny to Evil the satisfaction of hearing my admission to defeat. This is assuredly a noble vision – something that could, at times, make us alleged religious believers ashamed to think of how easily we get

discouraged. I think this is akin to Bonhoeffer's calling us to 'live before God as if there were no God'.

Jean-Paul Sartre (1905-1980)

Jean-Paul Sartre became something of a cult figure in the 1960s. Frequenting the famous bistro Aux Deux Magots, just opposite the church of Ste. Germaine des Pres, along with Simone de Beauvoir, and enjoying the adulation he received from leftist student groups in the heady days of 'May 68'. When Gabriel Marcel learnt that Sartre had purloined the term existentialism to describe his rather dogmatic atheistic nihilism (Marcel had coined the term to indicate the focus of his own manner of thinking), Marcel dropped the word and declared that he should be called a 'christian socratist'. He had no wish to have his views classified under the same rubric of his contemporary, Sartre.

I have qualified Sartre's brand of atheism (and nihilism) as dogmatic. In doing this I am not overlooking the somewhat questionable metaphysics he proffers us in *Being and Nothingness*¹⁰. There, quite arbitrarily he tells us that there are but two types of beings in his ontology – *être en soi* (being in itself) and *être pour-soi* (being for itself). The former comprises all those beings that are objects (as opposed to conscious subjects – which are *être pour-soi*). The former imply a certain fixity, no scope for spontaneity, freedom or development: these are static beings. They *are*: they have attained a certain stability and state of finishedness. Subjects (*être pour-soi*) are not so much being but *becoming*: they are dynamic. Since they have no fixed nature, they must 'make themselves'. Since they have no in-written or preordained nature they must freely decide what they want to be, through their carefully chosen actions.

Thus, in one fell (and whimsically arbitrary) swoop, Sartre has defined God out of existence. Because for God to exist, he would have to combine in himself two impossible sets of qualities. He would have to be conscious (*être pour-soi*) as well as stable – for inasmuch as he would have to be a perfect being, God would be incapable of further development – and that would make him an *être en-soi*. But by decree of the *Maître*, Jean-Paul Sartre, all that is must be either *en-soi* or *pour-soi*: you can't have it both ways. So God can't exist. Q.E.D.!

Denis O'Brien has interestingly called Sartre 'the first serious atheist of the Christian tradition'¹¹. Atheists there had been before Sartre, but each had invariably come up with an alternative to function as a kind of Supreme Being and give meaning and value to life and existence: nature, humanity, the State, Love and so on. But Sartre is quite adamant: only a Necessary being could give life a meaning, a purpose and a significance. In the face of that absence, we must admit that life is meaningless, absurd and pointless.

The consequence of this is a terrible and frightening sense of loneliness and abandonment. As Orestes, in *The Flies*, puts it: "... alone, like a leper. I felt all alone, in the middle of my benign little world, like someone who has lost his shadow"¹². Or, as Matthieu cries out, in *The Reprieve*, "Cast out. Cast out of the world. Cast out from the past. Cast out from my own past."¹³

But suddenly there appears what seems to be a ray of hope. True, all is contingent and absurd, neither humans nor sub-humans have any essence which might justify their existence. Yet, as the same Orestes, observes in an initially exuberant moment of discovery, "I am free...freedom has broken upon me like a thunderbolt." More soberly (and, hence, all the more alarmingly), Sartre declares in his 800-page 'phenomenological ontology', *Being and Nothingness*, 'I am my liberty'¹⁴. (Emphasis added). As he goes on to clarify it: "freedom coincides at its roots with the non-being which is at the heart of man"¹⁵. At every moment it is our responsibility to invent values and give meaning to a meaningless world. The terrifying thing is that each of us must do this in isolation, without seeking for guidelines or essences: there aren't any.

So relentless and so exhausting are the demands of the responsibility of freedom that most of us abdicate this burden and, to make matters worse, trot out all manner of bogus justifications and excuses to cover up our cowardice. This is what Sartre calls *mauvaise foi* (literally, bad faith, that is, insincerity or hypocrisy) and this, according to me, is Sartrean sin!

Freedom brings anxiety (*angoisse*) and this is a terrifying onus: we must choose, we don't know how to choose (for there are no criteria to guide us) and every choice we make somehow suggests to others

that they follow our example (they shouldn't, but humans being such...). Anxiety upsets us and 'we can only escape this upsetting thought by a kind of bad faith'¹⁶.

Now the most common loophole out of which to construct our insincere escapes from the burden of freedom is through human relationships. We imagine we have found our meaning in life through friendship or love affairs. But, given the Sartrean understanding of freedom, all interpersonal relationships are doomed or, to be more precise, totally impossible. Given the fact that each person is freedom, when two people meet two independent worlds collide. The only way for relationships to succeed in such a context is for one freedom to capitulate before the other (or be annihilated by it). In other words, as Sartre likes to put it, every friendship is either a disguised form of sadism or of masochism. If one allows the others freedom to eclipse or suffocate one's own, he is masochist (claiming to have found meaning in self-immolation); if one simply goes ahead and dominates and destroys another's freedom or self, he is a sadist (claiming to have found fulfilment in the destruction of another). The first are cowards (*lâches*) for they give way before the other; the latter are bastards (*salauds*) because they have no scruples about overwhelming and wiping out their 'friend'! "Those who will hide, either with full intent or by pleas of determinism, their total liberty, I call cowards. Those who try to show their existence was necessary, though contingency envelopes the appearance of man on the earth, I call bastards."¹⁷

There is no way out of *mauvaise foi* in Sartre's philosophy. Once you grant him his questionable understanding of freedom, a monstrous thing. For Sartre freedom exists as long as I say, "No!". once I say 'Yes!' I have lost my freedom. Sartrean sin could also be defined as the act of saying, 'yes'. Thus freedom, for Sartre, isolates us from each other more and more. As someone in his controversial play *Huis Clos*¹⁸ puts it, "*L'enfer c'est l'autre!*" (Hell is the Other). Paul Ricoeur offers us a valuable corrective, here: he reminds us that ours is an incarnate freedom; it is rooted (like us) in the world and, though it is a genuine freedom, it cannot be totally independent of nature and nurture, heredity and environment¹⁹. Indeed, the climactic act of freedom is to say a humble 'yes' in an authentic community. Only when we can do that do we really attain the fullness of freedom.

B: Postmodernism

At the outset, let me observe, in passing, that there is no hyphen in *postmodernism*, unlike post-colonialism, post-industrialism and similar indicates some measure of temporal posterity: for instance, post-colonialism implies a time when colonialism was dead and buried and post-industrialism implies that post-industrialism entered the scene after industrialism had breathed its last. Postmodernism, however, points to an attitude, a climate of thinking, that had its origins prior to modernism and often ran concurrent with it.

The name *modernism* is associated with Descartes and those of his ilk who came, more or less, after the Enlightenment of fifteenth and sixteenth century Europe. They wanted to distinguish themselves from the 'Dark' or 'Middle' Ages, which they tended to disparage as dominated by superstition and intolerance. The great redeeming feature of their times, of which many 'moderns' were immensely proud, was that the age of science, of experiment and observation, was part of their era. René Descartes (1596 – 1650) was the father of rationalism: reason, not faith, would be *the* characteristic of the next two centuries. Science, not philosophy or theology (or religion), would offer humans a solution for all their ills, and it would be the scientist who would take over the role of the priest as humankind's great liberating figure.

We were not long into the next two centuries – the nineteenth and the twentieth – than a series of events added fuel to the fires of doubt and suspicion with which many had begun to view proud reason and the apparently tall claims of science. Some form of anti-rationalism has always been part and parcel of human history and postmodernism was its legitimate offspring. A number of developments in science suddenly made it abundantly clear that reason had its limitations (some would even call it a fraud) and scientists were forced to admit that they weren't so cocksure of their findings. Einstein's Theory of Relativity, Heisenberg's Uncertainty Theory, Quantum Mechanics and a host of other scientific breakthroughs seemed to expose the hollowness of the pretensions of pure reason and the until-then epistemological certainties that had been trundled out by the scientist began to totter and collapse. Post-modernism could now take centre stage: no longer had it to be content with the role of an irritable gadfly, sitting in the wings or haunting the background. No discipline can give us certainty

it began to proclaim, loudly and boldly: neither philosophy nor religion, not even science. Everything is up for grabs, everything is relative.

Postmodernism was first bandied about as a very moral attitude. It was touted as the great philosophy of liberation that all oppressed minorities had been waiting for. The main thesis of one of its most prophetic voices, whose *The Postmodern Condition*²⁰ – often hailed as ‘the Bible of Postmodernism’ – was that “postmodernism is nothing more than incredulity towards metanarratives”. This term which its creator Jean-Francois Lyotard (1924 – 1998) bequeathed to posterity and was snapped up by social activists and would be liberators everywhere referred to any universal or grand theory that was put forward as a kind of universal panacea to the human condition, irrespective of time and place: Christianity, Marxism, Islam, Humanism and so on. Lyotard’s anti-authoritarianism and anti-foundationalism are all the more evident by the way he presented the legitimation of power and authority in his work. Contrary to the popular conviction, he pointed out, metanarratives justified their position not so much by argumentation and proof based on pure reason – as was claimed and believed – but simply by the manipulation of money and power: capitalism and weapons of mass destruction. Yes, America with its almighty dollars and ranking as the world’s only superpower was the villain of the piece. Conquerors wrote the first colonial histories and presented themselves as doing a favour to the natives they brought under their sway, depicting them as immoral and uncultured savages to whom they brought the benefits of religion and civilisation. The Great White Mother – England, France, Spain, Holland or Portugal – would bleed exploit indigenous people and, to add insult to injury, would say that all this was for their own good.

Postmodernism sought to unveil the hypocrisy and unjust structures upon which international set-ups were built and, as anyone who knows the history of colonised nations and their colonial masters, will agree, it was easy to find abundant evidence in favour of this hypothesis. Many fledgling liberative movements – those concerning women²¹, homosexuals²² and indigenous people²³ found the words of Lyotard, Foucault, Derrida and Baudrillard a kind of shot-in-the-arm to revitalise their membership and activities. The great ‘sin’ that post-modernism was so boldly and cleverly laying bare was what we might call ‘structural

sin' those unjust structures and false values upon which international and intra-national networks are built and which serve as effective and efficient brakes for the development of oppressed people, ensuring that the dominant groups maintain successfully their stranglehold on world economy and culture, while yet posing as the great and universal benefactors of the human race.

But suddenly, all the hope and promise turned to dust and ashes. Oppressed minorities, rejuvenated at first by the insights and encouraging message of postmodernism, suddenly found that their would-be champions had pulled away the carpet under their feet and they were lying abandoned once again. And this for metaphysical and epistemological reasons. They had trained their guns so successfully on the inadequacies of Cartesian reason and Cartesian subjectivism – caricatures of the genuine article, if ever there were such – that a most destructive and nihilistic relativism (which Benedict XVI is ever inveighing against) and splintering fragmentation could only result. If everything is equally true (or false) and there is no way to establish any criteria of truth or beauty or morality, what other way would there be to win an argument but brute force and capital? Which reinstates the very people and forces we had begun to campaign against. And if there is nothing that can have universal application (because any common human nature or whatever would partake of a metanarrative) then no group – be it women, dalits or homosexuals – could have any basis to rally around and unite themselves about. Nor could one explain why democracy should seek to overthrow racism or male chauvinism: there is no criterion to decide which is bad and which is good.

All this is not to deny the fact that postmodernism has some very salutary truths for all of us to reflect upon. Michel Foucault (1926 – 1984) showed, through his painstaking research on hospitals and the way they work, how there is some amount of truth in his startling assertion that humans have a morbid fascination for locking some target people up and spying upon their behaviour²⁴. Jacques Derrida (1930 – 2004) showed that many of our dogmatic and glib assertions are based on false value, 'constructs' that very often can be dismantled into nigh nothingness, as one goes on peeling an onion²⁵. Jean Baudrillard (1929 -), for all his shallow eclecticism, has forcibly brought to our attention how the media is making an artificial world (simulacra) replace the

real world for many unthinking and uncritical people²⁶. All these contemporary sins of our IT world need to be highlighted, lest we barter away our liberty for a mess of pottage and cheap bagatelle. Every error is an exaggerated truth!

Conclusion

We have exposed how some contemporary philosophers view the human construct of evil and injustice in the world – ‘sin’ for them. I have deliberately confined myself to the more striking insights of atheistic thinkers to show that the traditional identification of the atheist with immorality is as foolish and out-dated as the equally traditional equation of religious belief with naivety and ignorance. This may now be something of a hackneyed truism but for all that it keeps coming back in a myriad of guises so it is not out of place to repeat it.

The proper response to the deficiencies of Cartesian modernism is not the response of the extreme view of postmodernism, but a rehabilitation of authentic reason as per the work of Habermas²⁷ as well as that of authentic subjectivism as per the research of Ken Wilber²⁸. I have delved deep enough into this elsewhere and this is neither the time nor the place to rehearse that effort²⁹.

Notes and References

- 1 Pastoral Constitution on the Church in the Modern World, no. 19. Its official Latin title is *Gaudium et Spes* and it was voted through by the Council Fathers on December 7, 1965, at St. Peter’s under the papacy of Paul VI.
- 2 This is the title of the famous work by Henri de Lubac, sj (transl. by Edith M. Riley, New York, Sheed & Ward, 1950). Though written long before the age of the dialogue launched by Vatican II, it is both a critical and sympathetic study and acknowledges that atheists ‘even at their most blasphemous...advance criticisms whose justice (the Christian) is bound to admit.’ (cf. the Preface)
- 3 In his *Existentialism and Humanism* (trsl. Bernard Frechtman), New York, the Philosophical Library, 1957). This is the text of a lecture given in 1946, short and to the point. The French title reads *Existentialism is a Humanism* and better expresses the intent of Sartre as regards this work: a response to his critics who had dubbed his brand of existentialism anti-human.
- 4 Ibid

- 5 This was and over hasty conclusion drawn from Heidegger's *Sein und Zeit*, published just the year before Sartre's *Existentialism and Humanism*. In his *Letter on Humanism* Heidegger points out that in the work referred to he had neither affirmed nor denied God. He goes on to write, 'thus it is not only rash but also an error in procedure to maintain that the interpretation of the essence of man from the relation of his essence to the truth of Being is atheism'. And he reminds us that he had said the same thing in his *The Essence of Reasons* (trsl. Terrence Mallick), Evanston, Northwestern University Press, 1969: the German original dates from 40 years earlier!
- 6 Albert Camus, *The Plague* (trsl. Stuart Gilbert), New York, Alfred A. Kopf Inc., 1948.
- 7 Cf. his *The Rebel* (trsl. Anthony Power, with a Preface by Sir Herbert Read), New York, Alfred A. Kopf Inc., 1958.
- 8 Cf. his *The Myth of Sisyphus* (trsl. Justin O'Brien), New York, Alfred A. Kopf Inc., 1955.
- 9 Cf. Dietrich Bonhoeffer, *Letters and Papers from Prison* (ed. Eberhard Bethge; trsl. Reginald Fuller), London: SCM Press, 1967 (3rd ed.). in this controversial work, Bonhoeffer urges the prophetic person to 'live before God as if there were no God' or, as he puts it in Latin 'etsi Deus non daretur': meaning, at least, according to my reading – that when we speak up or act for justice, we should not expect God to intervene to save us or make our sufferings any less, when the powers that be attack us, torture us and, perhaps even, put us to a terrible and lonely death. Though we live, in faith, 'before God', in the hour of crisis we should not be scandalised if God does not come to deliver us: at such times we have to live 'as if there were no God'. This means that, in practice, Bonhoeffer's prophet and Camus' rebel, at the existential level, experience the same situation, phenomenologically speaking.
- 10 (trsl. Hazel Barnes), New York, Washington Square Press, 1967. As everyone knows, a more readable (and shorter!) version of this tome is Sartre's *La Nausee*, Paris, Gallimard, 1938 (which somewhat predated the more abstract work).
- 11 In an interesting article in *Commonweal*, July 4, 1980.
- 12 Cf. Jean-Paul Sartre, *No Exit and Three Other Plays* (trsl. Stuart Gilbert and others), New York, Random House, Vintage Books, 1949. One of the 'Other Plays' printed here is *The Flies*, which dates from 1943 – during the Nazi occupation of Paris – and uses the myth of Orestes to propound Sartre's views on freedom.
- 13 Jean-Paul Sartre, *The Reprieve* (trsl. Eric Sutton). Hammonds worth, Penguins, 1970. This is the second volume of a trilogy – the first part is entitled

The Age of Reason and the last Iron in the Soul. Begun in 1945, it is a study of the life of Matthieu Delarue, a hero who emerges from the back streets of Paris and is slowly drawn into the awesomeness of commitment when World War II breaks out and France faces war and ignoble defeat. Matthieu and his friends keep hoping that war will be averted and they'd be spared from having to make terrible commitments, but this is not to be.

14 Being and Nothingness.

15 Ibid

16 In Existentialism and Humanism.

17 Ibid.

18 Cf. No Exit and Three Other Plays. Another English translation of the same play calls it In Camera.

19 Paul Ricoeur, Freedom and Nature: the Voluntary and the Involuntary (transl. Erazim Kohak), Evanston, Northwestern University Press, 1965. The last chapter is especially relevant, in this connection.

20 In 1979, the University of Quebec commissioned him to write *La Condition Postmoderne*, which was republished in English as *The Postmodern Condition: A Report on Knowledge*, in 1984.

21 Women's Liberation activists were among the first to turn to postmodernism to recharge their arsenal. Almost all of them are French nationals. There is Julia Kristeva (Bulgarian born), Luce Irigaray, Helene Cixous.

22 Michel Foucault was homosexual, himself. Though openly gay within his own circle, he never really 'came out of the closet' to the public at large. He was quite active in gay politics, but was never strident about it. When he died in 1984 his family, at first, refused to admit that he had succumbed to AIDS.

23 The most famous of all these was Chinua Achebe, the Nigerian activist. Cf., especially his *Things Fall Apart*.²⁴ When on a stint teaching French at Upsala, Sweden, he chanced upon a library of medical works from the sixteenth to the twentieth centuries. Thence he gathered most of the material he would use in his later writings on the history of the hospitals in general and of how we treat 'insane' and 'abnormal' persons. His 600-page study *Folie et deraison* was published in 1961, followed by two volumes in 1984. The English title was *Madness and Civilisation*. The next study came out in 1963. The English title is *The Birth of the Clinic* and has the sub-title "The Archaeology of the Medical Gaze". "This book", Foucault informs us in the opening pages, "is about space, about language and about death; it is about the act of seeing the gaze." In short, it treats about our alleged morbid fascination to lock up deviants and then watch how they behave –

culminating in the panopticum, the all-seeing eye, which contemporary technology makes possible.

- 25 This is a fair image of Derrida's process of deconstruction.
- 26 Baudrillard takes delight in coming out with all manner of outlandish and shocking phrases, such as "The Gulf War Never Took Place!" What he means is that the Gulf War that we know is what CNN and the media showed us: a far cry from the real thing. Again, he tells us that the great myth of "The American Way of Life" is only incarnate in Disneyland!
- 27 Juergen Habermas of the Frankfurt school, great rehabilitator of Reason against the caricature of it by Descartes and the attacks on it by the postmodernists who, unbeknownst to them were but flinging stones at a caricature of it, which is what the Cartesian version of it was!
- 28 The Chicagoan Ken Wilber is an excellent rehabilitator of the authentic human subject, from the ravages of Descartes.
- 29 I would refer the interested reader to my *Postmodernism*, Pune, Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, 2001 where, making use of both Habermas and Wilber, I have a critique of the postmodern thinkers and a summary of what we can gain from them in the last chapter.